

SattvaGuna Enrichment Programm (Course) - An Effective MOOC

Dr. Madhuvanti Kulkarni

Assistant Professor, S.P.S. College of Education, Sangli,
Affiliated to Shivaji University. Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

INTRODUCTION

E-education is not entirely new concepts. It is grown in each country. It is taking roots for Indian students as well. One can be provided the best education in the world direct from the persons who wrote the courses for online study. The courses are available for any subject and the levels can be from beginner to higher advances. Individual could find the right course and course level without difficulty. In the 21st Century, students may stay at home and take education across the world. E-education system includes the development of e-materials. Teaching students online, governing students online, providing the infrastructure and support within which e-education can operate, planning and managing e- education. Today MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) is one of the way for geographically dispersed students for participation in web based, free distance learning programme. The word 'MOOC' was coined in 2008 by Dave Cormier (University of Manitoba). 2012 was a big year of MOOCs. In this year, various types of MOOCs became well known throughout the world.

The Digital Literacy Mission was announced as a part of Union Budget 2016 to cover 60 million rural households within next three years, "Digital Highways" that are being created as a part of the "Digital India Mission" will play an important role in connecting India and Bharat. We do believe that the full impact of Digitalization in Education will play become stronger in 2018 and beyond.

Today's students search for university or colleges offering subjects of their choice. Then they enroll for the courses without stepping out of their houses. The students don't have to deal with traffic or boring lectures while persuing the course. Craig (2015)

shows the pressure created by the rising cost of higher education and the free offerings of MOOCs. He made the people understand for the first time that the different components of an education offering could be supplied by companies. Various courses in various fields were designed by different organizations related to MOOC. The emergence and use of MOOC for professional teacher development is still uncommon. Researches published were very less on this concept .Over 6.5 million students have enrolled in over 800 free courses from over 200 different learning institutions (Gallagher and Garrett,2013).There are numerous MOOC providers .

Role of the University in MOOC

The Role of the University is to make available these courses to students because Excellent students who could not be accepted as onsite students in prestige universities, due to lack of financing and constraints as to how many can fit into onsite classrooms. These students face new opportunities to get a prestige degree in their own homes.

There is nothing particularly new about MOOCs. Most universities have provided online courses for many years. The only difference is the scale. MOOCs are built on efficiency of scale. Lectures, assessments and activities and the expertise of the professor are unique to a particular university. Because of the scale direct and physical involvement by the faculty member is limited. This shifts the responsibility on the shoulders of the individual students and their motivations to learn. MOOC courses can start any time and can be of any length. That makes the MOOC compelling for short term courses that are highly focused on topic or a series of courses that might

build towards a deeper understanding in a knowledge area. They can be offered with a certificate. The credential can be separate from the class itself. University can take the advantage of the format of MOOCs. So the courses can solve the problems in higher education.

MOOCs can be a way for universities to offer high quality, self paced courses to fill the needs at a minimal cost to students. Since MOOCs are not bound by the academic calendar, it could be broken into smaller units of a few weeks that students can take during summer breaks or other times that fit better with their overall schedule. More importantly, it could help high school teachers to complete core courses at their school and give them the opportunity to work with students as mentors, guides and coaches in new, innovative ways.

An online course is available at significantly lower fees or no fees. Therefore, student is provided opportunity for higher education. Student also gets guidance from online tutors who are experienced and fulfill responsibilities. There is continuous use of computer to complete the online course. Therefore, there is improvement of student in computer based skills. Teachers need to keep up to date digital skills because their students will be demanding those skills.

Features of MOOCs

1. MOOC have course structure, goals, mile tones within a set of learning areas or specific topics
2. They are available online and allow connection in remote locations via Internet.
3. Their scope is massive. They allow the access of a large number of students.
4. Their contact is open, giving follow up. In regard to the ownership and license type of the content for its reuse there is no consistent approach and it depends on each platform.

SattvagGuna Enrichment Programme an Effective MOOC for all Teachers in the World

It is believed - right through the ages-that 'teaching' is a 'noble' profession. The teacher is liked, loved and admired - and in many cases- worshipped by the student. Not only the student, but the society at large also expects a lot from the teacher. Needless to say, the noble profession, naturally demands the teacher to be noble one, And here "the SattvaGuna Enrichment Programme" has a role to play. The Kothari Commission Report (1964-66) rightly remarks "The

future of a country is being shaped in today's classroom." Obviously, the role of the teacher who solely controls the "class" assumes immense importance. Hence, the researcher intended to prepare the SattvaGuna Enrichment Programme (SGEP) for teachers.

Younger children mostly imitate their parents more as compared to their teachers. But when they reach the adolescence, they become more aware of their 'self'. They become more independent of their parents. They are in a phase of "transition". They are in a mood of overthrowing the bindings of their parents and other elders in the family. They are continuously on the lookout for a "separate identity" of their own. They intend to free themselves from the "bonds and bindings" of their elders in general and parents - in particular. Obviously, this stage becomes a very delicate but decisive in nature. The situation demands somebody else who can replace the parents; who can fill the vacuum. And the only fitting answer is the "teacher". Hence, the researcher chose "the Secondary School Teacher" as her subject matter. Thus, the researcher intends to provide an ideal solution to the problems of the adolescence age-group of students.

According to the Bhagavad Gita (Vendanta Samiti, Bhagavad Gita As It Is, 1986, P. 609, 610) Sattva, Raja and Tama are three basic characteristics (Gunas) present in nature, in human being which are responsible for his/ her good or bad behaviour. Sattva binds through identification with satisfaction and wisdom. On the other hand Raja which is of the nature of passion, as born of greed of gain and attachment, it binds the soul through attachment to actions and their fruit and Tama, deceptive of all those who look upon the body as their own self, as born of ignorance, it binds the soul through error, laziness and sleep.

Thus, it is clear that Sattvaguna has positive effects on personality and therefore desirable than Raja and Tama. Therefore, it is essential that a programme to enrich Sattvaguna should be prepared and tested. Teacher is an agent of social reconstruction hence, there is a argent need to develop programme to enrich Sattvaguna among the teachers. Teenagers are highly, flexible minded and receptive to 'Sanskaras' they have. They look to the teachers as their ideal models. Hence, Secondary School Teachers have a large scope as well as responsibility to create ideal citizens of the

country. Hence, the researcher has chosen secondary school teachers as participants.

The study will be useful to get guidelines for Teachers. It will also provide guidelines to other professional organizations for arranging personality development programme. The present study is based on Indian Psychology and Philosophy. Researcher studied various related researches. Efforts have been made to establish relation between Indian Psychology and Education. The researcher has conducted SGEP programme. She has thought of applicability of the findings of her research, in the 21st century Education. The SattvaGuna Enrichment Programme (SGEP) is aimed at the teacher because he is the one and only person having authority and responsibility both and accountability, too, in shaping the personality and building the character of his student.

As already stated the need for such programmes will go on increasing.

Five characteristics have been focused on to develop SattvaGuna among the teachers. These are i) Awareness about Sattvik Diet. ii) Positive Attitude iii) Satisfaction of mind. iv) Steadiness of mind. v) Teaching competency.

All these characteristics should be present in the personality, of a teacher. If the teachers are deficient in possessing these qualities, a training programme needs to be conducted that would develop these qualities among the teachers. The researcher has made an attempts to provide such a programme. She has named her programme as ‘SattvaGuna Enrichment Programme’. She has prepared it for the Secondary School Teachers but she thinks that her SGEP is applicable to the teachers at any level, in any country, in any community in the world.

In a fast changing world of today the Educators’ job is going to become more and more challenging. More attention shall have to be paid to character building of the student. The teachers shall have to serve as role models in the process of character building. The researcher is optimistic that her programme would prove to be a step forward in that direction.

Implementation of the SGEP

SGEP was implemented from 7th December, 2008 to 8th March, 2009 On Sundays.

Time chart of Program

Sr No.	Name of the Activity	Date / Time
01	Orientation and information about the Programme	7/12/08 8.30 am to 11.00 am
02	Pre-test VCD of a Lecture and Discussion Subject – Life history of Shri. Vishwas Nangre Patil, Lecture and Discussion Subject – Basic concept of ‘Trigunas’	14/12/08 8.30 am to 10.00 am 10.10 am to 12 am 12.00 am to 2.00 pm
03	Lecture and Discussion Subject-Concept of balanced diet and Classification of diet according to the concept of ‘Trigunas’ Lecture and Discussion Subject- Teacher & job Satisfaction related to ‘Trigunas’	21/12/08 9.00 am to 11.30 am 11.45am to 2.00 pm
04	Lecture and Demonstration Subject-Yoga for Teachers Lecture and Demonstration Subject- Stress reduction Model	28/12/08 9.00 am to 11.30 am 11.45 am to 2.00 pm
05	Lecture and Discussion Subject – Diet & Sleep A Film and Discussion – Wednesday	04/01/09 9.00 am to 11.30 am 11.45 am to 2.00 pm
06	Lecture and Discussion Subject–Sattvik Diet & Mental health Lecture and Demonstration Subject- Sahajyog, and Use of dhyana, Pranayam for teachers	08/01/2009 9.00 to 11.30 11.45 am to 2.00 pm
07	Poster – Presentation & different clippings from internet on positive thinking Discussion on different imaginary situations based on school camps	11/01/2009 9.00 am to 11.30 am 11.45 am to 2.00 pm

	Exchange of books and discussion	2-00 pm. to 2.30 pm
08	Discussion on Problems in life VCD- Life history of Dr. Raghunath Mashelkar,	24/01/2010 9.00 am to 11.30 am 11.45 am to 2.00 pm
09	Audio CD- Lecture and Discussion Shri. Sunil Chincholka 'Dasbodh' – Trigun Vichar	1/02/2010 9.00 am to 11.30 am
09	Game and Discussion – My Circle	11.45 am to 2.00 pm
10	Lecture and Discussion Subject – Follow up Programme, solutions on various problems. Programme of Donation “Velankar Anathashram”, Radhakrishna Vasahat, Sangli.	8/02/2010 9.00 am to 11.30 am 11.45am to 2.00 pm
11	Follow up Programme	10.00 am to 1.00 pm

Concluding Remarks

The researcher conducted the programme for three months as scheduled in the research process. After a month she conducted a follow up programme. The SGEP as a part of research ended with the follow up programme but the participant teachers collectively requested the researcher to continue with such programmes. They demanded that even after completing the research work, the researcher and the teachers interested should continue with the activities included in SGEP. They want the researcher to conduct the activities at least once every month on regular basis. This self-evidently indicates that SGEP has come out to be immensely effective and useful from the teachers point of view.

Thus, the researcher is satisfied with the results. She hopes that it will be useful for future study and different courses in education as well as it will be useful as a MOOC.

Actually SattvaGuna is more important in the Education Sector. Above Programme should be used as a course .In the course, audio- Video conferencing, Test material, Notes, Videos. Resources are ready. Therefore it will be useful for the development of MOOC.

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